

Ramkrishna Mukherjee on the dynamics of agrarian class and economic structure of colonial Bengal: A critical study

Anindya Datta*

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Abstract

The following article, demonstrates the works of Ramakrishna Mukherjee's contributions, in the field of agrarian studies of India. The article critically examined the context, his perspectives, the ideas he brought forwarded and its contemporary relevance.

Key words: class, rural society, Permanent Settlement, production relations

Introduction

Ramakrishna Mukherjee (RKM) made a significant contribution to diverse aspects of Indian sociology. His contributions are so diverse that it is impossible to do justice to the full range of his works in a single article. The author, therefore, undertook to highlight just one area of his scholarship, namely RKM's analysis of agrarian class and economic structure of colonial Bengal. Many other social scientists have also dwelt on agrarian society in colonial Bengal. By comparing and contrasting RKM's understanding of colonial agrarian society with those of other scholars, this author seeks to break new ground in studying Ramakrishna Mukherjee's sociology.

Agrarian class and economic structure of Bengal

Ramakrishna Mukherjee's (R.K.M.) view on class structure of agrarian society could be traced to two of his major studies on agrarian socio-economic structure. One of them was his micro study namely: "Six Villages of Bengal" which he undertook at an early stage of his life, during the period 1942-43 and written in 1946, it was, however, published as a form of complete book in the year 1971; in his words "The book was written in 1946. village society which was caused by the differentiation in the agrarian economic structure.

*The author is a research scholar of the Department of Sociology, The University of Burdwan

It was published as a "paper" in the journal of Asiatic Society of Bengal, and ---- Written nearly a quarter of a century earlier, the book will now attain for the first time a status of its own " (Mukherjee, 1971); and the other was the macro study under the title "Dynamics of a rural society" published in the year 1957. In both of the studies he depicted the stratification of

His studies portrayed "the relation between different institutions and groupings" in rural area, the everyday life of rural people towards accomplishment of their economic activities, and "the relations they entered into by so doing" (Mukherjee, 1971). He refuted the traditional and Colonial concept of Indian rural society being "Egalitarian" which was said to remain unchanged for centuries; and he also criticised the eventual stance of the so called social scientists for not taking up rural society seriously for research considerations. (Colonial view had been evidently cited by him through The Report (p.6) of the Royal Commission on Agriculture in India noted in 1928 "The desire to accumulate money is not characteristic of rural society", (See also The Report of the Indian Statutory Commission, Vol. 1, p. 18; M.A. Huque's The Man Behind the Plough, p.vi; etc.) (Mukherjee, 1957) He estimated rural society to be conspicuously structured and had not been static but dynamic. Hence he sought to examine the structural changes that were gradually taking place in the agrarian society; and for which he considered the assessment of economic structure is necessary because they are correlated. Thus he wrote in the preface of his book The Dynamics of a Rural Society:

The objective behind the present study is to examine the dynamics of a rural society and to show that the dynamic of a society cannot be revealed without any analysis of its economic structure. This is a stand point which for rural societies is not entertained by all social scientists. (Mukherjee, 1957)

The conventional view which pronounced that the "peasants" are a collection of "undifferentiated or little differentiated homogeneous mass"; and it is thus unlikely, to determine their economic structure. It is, therefore, needless to study peasant society. Contrary to this view he claimed with evidence from his rigorous village study that economic structure of village society can be determined and through the analysis of such economic structure

the dynamics or the changes in the social order can be unravelled.

He presented a variety of data from different sources demonstrating different income categories existing within the limit of rural Bengal in British period. It may therefore be said that "inequality in income distribution leading to a sharp differentiation" (Mukherjee, 1957). Thus to break the myth of "egalitarian" trait of village society of Bengal he encouraged a thorough assessment of its economic structure. However, this assessment should not turn into a mere statistical or mathematical segregation of rural collective disregarding social factors. It would be such an assessment which should pay due attention to the existential life of the village people while determining their economic status. He considered three major elements to categorise rural collectives into some distinct stratum. These elements were village (resident of specific rural location), religion (members of particular caste or community) and household occupation (livelihood from a particular family or household occupation). However, he deemed household occupation was only secular element out of three which assisted classification without bias. He thus extracted nine occupational categories (groups) based on household occupation as 1.Landholders, 2.Supervisory farmers, 3.Cultivators, 4.Sharecroppers, 5.Agricultural Labourers, 6.Artisans, 7.Traders, 8.Service-holders and 9.Others. However in his earlier micro study on agrarian socio-economic structure namely "Six Villages in Bengal" he broadly classified rural society into three economic groups on the basis of agrarian relations of production:

Landlords upon whose lands "industry of the village expanded". There might be individuals or "group relations holding joint property".

Petty farmers/cultivators, they hold rented lands or small holdings over which they have right of occupancy.

Landless persons who act as sharecroppers or labourer

He also talked about Artisans who were engaged in small-scale home industries such as indigenous craft etc. some of them served the basic needs of the rural community by weaving, oil pressing, carpentry and tailoring shop and peddling food grains etc from one village to another. He extracted household occupation of three sorts: agriculture, industry or trade and a

combination of both. Household occupations were commonly carried on unitedly and mutually; one's contributions to the whole operation of the work could hardly be measured, because one's work was not benchmarked in terms of money value as did in Industrial system at urban setup. He also minutely illustrated the nature of a range of trade and callings in his micro study of Six Villages such as: Carpentry, tailoring, tinkering, weaving, oil pressing, shop-keeping, money lending etc.

However, he generalized his findings (Six Villages of Bengal) of various household occupations as well as trade and callings into nine occupational categories which were (as already mentioned above) categorically divided into three classes:

The Class I consisted of the occupational groups of Landholders and Supervisory farmers, i.e., 'subinfeudatory landlords' and the affluent non-cultivating or supervisory farmers whose social status was unquestionably high in rural society.

The class II chiefly composed of the self-reliant/ self sufficient farmers that was Cultivators who managed to sustain their self-reliant /self-sufficient existence partially on their land. In this category, artisans, traders, service-holders were also included for their self-reliant nature of earning bread.

The class III indicated the residues of the occupational groups such as sharecroppers, agricultural-labourers and others, who were largely dependent on working for other members of the society, sometimes, of course, on the charity of the affluent section of the rural society.

Thus, after segregating the economic structure of the agrarian society into three homogeneous economic groups he felt such classification would be rather mechanical if the production relations among them were not considered. He thereby sought to comprehend various production relations arising out of the interactions of these three classes. In this connection it is interesting to pinpoint his rationale hereunder:

The economic structure of a society, however, is not revealed merely by segregating the people into homogeneous units of similar economic status. For man is the producer of his means of livelihood, and therefore the operation of an economy is the total manifestation of the

interrelationship of the people in regard to the production of wealth in society. Consequently the composition of the economic structure should be the total representation of the different types of production relations which the people have entered into in course of their economic activities" (Mukherjee, 1957)

Economic structure was thus the reflection of the entirety of the various production relations in the class divided agrarian society, the nature of which could be determined by the nature of ownership of the means of production of that society. This is important to note here that his understanding of economic structure of rural society hence emphatically expresses his ideological base which was no doubt dialectical, the Marxist one; however, his interpretation of agrarian society and its classification were dependent on his pragmatic choice which directs not to be a copy-bookish in interpreting Indian agrarian society, rather to consider its given situation and culture.

His efforts to establish the fact, that these three classes forming agrarian economic structure, therefore, needed an assessment as to how they differentiated themselves in terms of their production relations. According to him the agrarian society of Bengal had been distinctly stratified in line with the socio-economic hierarchy since its inception along with a small section of non agricultural occupants i.e., the holders of different callings and trades whose activities were essentially, though not directly, linked with agrarian economy. This agrarian socio-economic structure would have been remained almost stagnant with or without gradual or imperceptible changes for centuries if not British Imperialism appeared in the socio-economic arena of the rural Bengal.

With the advent of British rule in India the land property right had been established in rural Bengal through "permanent settlement", and thereby a perceptible change had been registered in socio-economic structure as well as in production relations and also in the nature of ownership of the means of production. Considering the juncture of this transitional phase of village economy he made an attempt to assess the roles played by these three classes. The class I which accommodates "landed gentry" viz, landlords and supervisory farmers who did not actively take part in agricultural work, however, they compiled surpluses from the ownership of

land which became the chief means of production at the sweat of agricultural labourers, and gradually this class went on concentrating the land resources to earn more surpluses. To establish his point he cited Surveyed data of 1946 as here under, "According to the 1946 survey data, they accounted for only 4 per cent of the total households of rural Bengal has owned 11 per cent of the total land. In other words, this class possesses two and three quarters more than what it could claim in case of an equitable distribution" (Mukherjee, 1957). The Class II of the agrarian socio economic structure composed of self-reliant as well as self-cultivating peasants with land property right (permanent settlement). This implied that their ownership of the means of production was established by the Colonial Acts. They exploited only their own labour in order to accumulate wealth which brought forth their dominant position in rural society.

From his works therefore we identify two classes of owners in agrarian economic structure: a) Class I who compiled wealth as well as surpluses by exploiting the labours of share croppers and agricultural labourers who were among Class III; and b) Class II who accumulated wealth by exploiting none but their own labour.

Lastly, the Class III consisting mostly of sharecroppers with or without meagre land of their own, Landless labourer and occupation holders of non agricultural nature such as craftsmen and traders. They all offered their labours, rather sold their labours or services/products to class I for their subsistence living. Thus the existence of the idea of "have not" and/or "petty bourgeois" is predominant in his writings. He found a curious production relation between Class I and Class III whereas Class II stood alone:

The operation of the economy of rural Bengal in the British period of her history is thus seen to have been dependent on two sets of productions – relations in society; one between the Classes I and III as owner and not-owner of the means of production (Land) and user and supplier of labour, respectively, and the other of the class II as the owner of the means of production and the user of the own labour (Mukherjee, 1957).

As declared earlier that author took keen interest in observing the quantum of change in economic structure if at all effected in the agrarian society of Bengal thus he sought to examine

extensively whether the production relations remained unchanged after the emergence of British rule and side by side, he also attempted to trace the genesis of class II, composed mostly of self-cultivating peasants. He evidently documented that the class II which, predominantly persisting in Indian agrarian socio-economic structure since the antiquity of Indian civilization, had always been the very basis our self-reliant or self sufficient village economy. It appears from this point of view that Indian society remained almost unchanged even after the advent of British rule which established the act of 'permanent settlement', R.K.M disagreed to the contemporaneous static view of agrarian socio-economic structure which insisted that the British rule did not bring forth any such change to agrarian society which might alter the enduring economic structure. The scholars attempt to make it evident that the persistence of a group of individuals related to agriculture without any 'usufructuary or property right' whose labours could be hired by cash or kind and who had thus been exploited by the gentry section throughout the centuries, could never be denied, and the situation remained all the same even after the advent of British rule. He never disagreed to the view, he was of the opinion that India being a caste divided society the upper caste occasionally called for labour to till their soil from lower castes and others such as Sudras, Dasas, Tribals or aboriginals with the assurance to be adopted in Varna system and even from conquered who were not familiar with plough cultivation. Thus this point he puts forward on contrary to the view of the most of present-day scholars who tend to equate the condition of present-day sharecroppers with that of the share croppers of pre British days.

The sharecroppers as well as the agricultural labourers hired by the upper crust of the social order were not exactly the same in nature as found in modern society, since they belonged to the lower strata of society and were employed as hired labourers and their usufructuary rights over land were unquestionable ,more over ancient Indian history ruled out the possibility of any existence of hired labourers in the self-reliant autonomous village of antiquity, it further emphasized on the importance of the role of self-cultivating peasantry who utilised and inherit their pieces of landholdings (hereditarily) to produce food grains for their subsistence, thus established their usufructuary right to landholdings, this right conferred to them by the village authority (which held as well as possessed

the arable and inhabitable lands as community wealth) was transferable or alienable. It is interesting to add here that the author jotted down few evidences from various sources to confirm that ancient Indian authority conferred peasants the right to possession of land, rather than right to ownership. Thus he wrote:

“---therefore, it seems reasonable to surmise that an individual's hold on land in ancient India was more in terms of possession than, strictly speaking, of ownership; so that land was used for subsistence production by direct producers instead of it being used as a property for profit-making and as a commodity to be bought and sold (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 20).

Right to possession of landholdings, therefore, led further to the dominant position of self cultivating peasants in rural economy in the pre-British period; and consequently they were the basis of the autonomous and self-sufficient village, and were the only producing class among the entire rural community.

Class I , together with Class III of the rural economic structure consisting on subinfeudatory landlords on one side and share-croppers, land-labourers and so forth, on the other were relatively absent in the scenario of Bengal under British rule. His concept on the existence of class I and Class III, however, contradicts with the view of such scholars as Colebrooke (he cites) who assured the presence of sharecroppers and the agricultural labourers at the time of Permanent Settlement (1793) and they were mentioned ,though insignificantly, in the Fifth Report of British Parliament, in which the role played by the Sharecroppers, Land-labourers including self-cultivating farmers or ryots and zemindars (revenue/supervisory farmers) in the production relation of the rural economy were discussed. Nevertheless, this report as well as other documents of East India Company mutually agreed upon the importance on autonomous character of the institution of Indian Village without any mention of landlords or zemindars who were presumed to be appeared forcefully the year afterwards 1793, marked by the enactment of Permanent Settlement of Zemindary. Zemindars existing in Bengal before the introduction of 'Permanent Settlement' as recorded by the Fifth Report, were nevertheless "accountable managers and collectors, and not lords and proprietors of the lands" (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 22)

The emergence of the classes I and III in the village economy of Bengal, according to him, was limited by certain facts, such as establishment of private property over land, system of landlordism and disintegration of village community should be taken to the first place. Dating back to year 1765 which marked the commencement of the British rule in Subha of Bengal, the East India Company rigorously attempted to take over the business from Indigenous merchants either by throwing them out of their business or by impelling them to sustain as their "agents". The exploitation was not limited to the traders only but it was prevalent in all the sphere of village economy – peasants, traders and artisans were all alike in the diction of exploitation. Artisans were forced to work for British officials or traders for meagre payments with which they could hardly maintain their bare subsistence, and farmers were made bonded labour for the production of commercial crops like indigo. Eventually a large sum of artisans left their customary vocation and took up agriculture and which thus strained the underdeveloped rural economy of Bengal to a certain extent.

All sorts of exploitation of the Company had so long been endured by Village community even to its extremity; but it started disintegrating only after the year 1793, when after a series of experimentation Lord Cornwallis' Permanent Settlement brought down a final regulation for the procedure of levying taxes which led to a decisive change in the land tenure system. Thus after the commencement of permanent zemindary act landlords as well as zemindars were employed permanently to collect tax from their territory which, according to him, established their proprietary right on land. That is to say the British ultimately conferred the right to "free transfer and absolute ownership – especially in the 'ryotwari' tracts – to the cultivators which they never possessed before" ¹

The above right brought about a sea change in the agrarian economic structure and resulted in - inequality of land distribution, pattern of the ownership of the means of production and the urge of earning surplus thus led to concentration and polarisation of land buttressed by the newly formed cult of zemindaries. If such

situation had never been aroused the self cultivating as well as self-sufficient peasantry, which at this instance turned into an endangered sect, would have perpetuated as only cultivating group of the self-sufficient village economy. This new situation, nevertheless helped much to the advent of the two new classes a) Landed Gentry and b) Disintegrated Peasantry.

The Landed Gentry belonged to the Class I which thus turned into a proprietor class started concentrating wealth in the form of land property and Class III which had no share of the ownership of means of production, and eventually having no alternative but to earn their daily bread by selling their labour for agricultural production.

He identifies the characteristics of the two rising classes, i.e., Class I and Class III. Class I consisting mostly of the parasitic land lords who were the agents of East India Company; but neither were they interested to cultivate their soil nor they had ever tried to improve cultivation with such measure as bringing up artificial irrigation to the arable lands and arrange such facilities which were much needed then to make the land fertile, in what were they really interested was to earn surplus in the form of commission and profits. Though a few benevolent landlords who previously were revenue farmers protested Company's oppressive policy and did not accept the continual increment of levies on arable lands, were soon replaced by such rapacious businessmen of lately emerged gentlemen category.

The condition of the farmers were getting most awful, they came increasingly under the chaff of pauperization enmeshed by the system of the British Rule. Moreover, burdened by the liability of taxes imposed arbitrarily by their overlords, their only way was to grow more, nevertheless poor infrastructure and amenities provided by this sub infeudatory system hindered their positive intention, they thus gradually sank into the indebtedness which further caused the dispossession of their own cultivating lands in the hands of money lenders.

Indigenous industrious efforts were mostly discouraged by the British imperialist and encouraged producers to be the mere suppliers of raw materials, resultantly indigenous industries were disintegrated, and the market for native or home-grown products was completely shattered, and foreign products took over the home market. Persons, engaged in home as well as small

¹ D.R. Gadgil – *Industrial Evolution*, p-28 as quoted in Mukherjee R.K. , *The Dynamics of A rural Society*, 1957

industries as their household occupations, being jobless now returned to village and took agricultural work, which stressed rural economy to a great extent.

Both the factors above had thereby created the impelling conditions which gave rise to Class III consisting mostly of agricultural labourers. It is interesting here to add that, since the industrial development in India in that period was so sluggish and sporadic that wage earners were almost absent from the scenario. The pauperized self-cultivating and self-sufficient peasants, having only experience to work in the agricultural field and no industrial exposure as such, had no options but to stay in the rural society taking the occupation of share cropping to earn their living. This is, in short the fact of the rise of two above classes.

After he analysed the factors for the emergence of class – I and Class – III, he then examined as to why such classes appeared within the agrarian economic structure with the advent of the British rule in Bengal. It is now important to note at this point, though this book was published in the year 1957, it seemed - at least this study (Mukherjee, *The Dynamics of A rural Society*, 1957) hints, he may have applied the same method of query which had been distinctly and repeatedly found in his studies since 1977 with the publication of *Trends in Indian Sociology* (1977) and continued in his subsequent publications of such admired books as *Sociology of Indian Sociology* (1979A); *What will it be? Exploration in Inductive Sociology* (1979B) and host of other books, till his last publication *Why Unitary Social Science?* . His method of query consisted of five questions (what? how? why? what will it be? and what should it be?ii) under a paradigmatic expression which, obviously according to his believe, facilitated to apprise any socio-economic phenomenon. The hints of his methodical application may thus be cited hereunder:

The above analysis, however, only explains how the classes I and III emerged in rural society of Bengal; it does not discuss why they emerged. This question “why” is, no doubt, of decisive importance in any scientific study, as otherwise it will not be realised how economic forces of rural Bengal found their expression through the economic structure composed of the three classes as defined previously. (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 40)

In order to examine why such classes emerged after pre-British period and its relation in specific with the enactment and establishment of “Permanent settlement in 1793 he keenly checked the historical background which existed as the precondition of their emergence. This era was marked by the continual increment in the number of agrarian wage labourers or share croppers. The system of sharecropping was buttressed as well as propagated by the parasitical landed gentry section that had been forcefully cropping up then. They controlled the agrarian mode of production in Bengal and thereby its rural economy. He denoted number of factors which contributed to the question as to why such increase in the number of sharecroppers occurred in that specific period. Among several factors he mentioned, few major factors may be discussed hereunder:

The landholders/zemindars , at that time had been increasingly attracted to make profit through tangible share of agricultural products, rather than the fixed revenue in the form of rent from the settled peasants. Thus they adopted various means to capture the land from ryots/self sufficient peasants and occupy it for their profits.

Due to excessive tax burden they (ryots) usually mortgaged their land to moneylenders and gradually the mortgaged lands were dispossessed from their hands due to non repayment of the sum taken from moneylenders. For greater profit the occupiers had created impelling conditions under which wage labourers were made to toil in the usurped lands. The lands, the chief means of production were concentrated by the parasitical gentry section which thus resulted in the rise of share croppers and the landholders as well.

A perceptible transformation of Indian trade policy also came to fore; two modes of British capital which thus played the influential roles to this process of change in trade and commerce in eighteenth and nineteenth centuries; they were the policies of British merchant capital and Industrial capital. The main intension of the merchant capital was to establish monopoly in trade along with the procurement of Indian goods in cheap rate which was only possible after the battle of Plassey (1757). Their Industrial capital encouraged India to reduce it to be a dumping ground for its products. Through their exploitative trade policies they not only increasingly devitalised indigenous trade and commerce but also shuttered some of the household industrial efforts such as weaving of

clothes, production of silk and muslins which might have otherwise affected their market in our country. Both the policies aimed to satisfy British Imperialistic interests which overburdened agricultural economy based on land; because a lot of household occupation holders other than agriculturists came into agricultural occupations.

This is more to add that for the analysis of the fact how merchant capital transformed into Industrial capital, R.K.M. emphatically illustrated with citations of the rampant plunder which had been made by the East India Company since the victory of the battle of Plassey. Practically the wealth accumulated by this plunder had been the chief source of the capital for the Industrial Revolution of late eighteenth century in Great Britain. The leaders of the industrial revolution – the capitalists who influenced the British political life to a great extent and stood firmly, though not benevolently, against the exploitation by the merchant capital, and intentionally, for their strategy of making India a market place for their merchandising efforts which is already mentioned above. They quite shrewdly followed the policy to make India a big warehouse of their own products so that they could easily win and control the (Asian) market. The setback of merchant capital in the face of industrial capital had resulted in ultimate collapse of East India Company due to its insolvency; and the stoppage of unrestrained ransacking of wealth had come at last.

Commodification of agricultural products encouraged by British industrial Trade policy, the use value of which could only be determined by the external trade, alienated peasants from the products they produced. Because the institutionalised practice of production being producing the means of subsistence, they were quite confused with the commercial crops and their utility, however they carried on producing them for the sake of their living.

Extraction of huge wealth from the Nawabs and other aristocrats of Bengal by the East India Company and its officers had resulted bankruptcy; and destruction of “normally developing economic life of Bengal”.

Company's craving to earn profits from the “estate farming” played a significant function soon after the authoritarian sceptre was taken over from the hands of Nawab of Bengal, as well as from landed aristocrats of various other provinces by the company.

Development of communication and transport in the middle of the 19th century – especially railways and steamer ways – marked the beginning of the industrial era in India under British rule. Communication through transport was mainly meant for bringing raw materials for British Industries from all parts of India, even from the farthest corner, to its main dockyards, with the intention to export to England. This advancement had resulted in the development of internal as well as external market for crops along with other agricultural products, and thereby increased its money value and, crops were thus transformed from substantial products to commercial products.

According to him, sum of all the factors contributed the rise of class III which was in most cases the transformation of self sufficient peasants and other occupation holders to sharecroppers or even wage labourer of land.

From the above view it is clear that self sufficient peasants were increasingly devitalised by the loss of lands, the chief means of their production which was the principal cause of their impoverishment, they did not however migrate to urban areas for the search of a new profession, because, being unskilled most of them could neither join industries (the development of which were also sluggish at the initial period) nor did they want to be uprooted from their own setup. They therefore, decided to stick to their places by taking up the occupation of sharecroppers and in the worst case, agricultural labourers. The conversion of self-sufficient peasants to sharecroppers or even to land labourers marked the emergence of class III on one hand; and on the other, the section of people who were mainly working as the permanent collection agents of British Govt. soon after the “permanent settlement” started concentrating lands by usurping them from self-sufficient peasants, emerged as class I.

In his concluding statement on the emergence of two classes he emphatically discussed the significant role of economic structure which, according to him, would help to appraise the “true character” of the agrarian society of Bengal under British rule, and also to determine how the economic forces working under the agrarian social structure. Thus, he indicated toward a new relation of production which took its origin at the cost of self-reliant nature of Bengal peasantry. This new relationship composed of a “Propertied” and a “property-less”

class, had a major drawback which pointed to the situation that, when at the same time traditional "peasant" farming had been sustained, the new production relation was made to adjust to the purpose of "commodity production". That is to say, while the tools and techniques of agriculture of Bengal were remained primordial, despite the development of agrarian production process British rulers insisted on commercialisation of agriculture.

He, therefore, pointed out not only a culture-lag in the process of agriculture but also indicated to a typical economic condition of Bengal under which, a new relation of production took its birth and envisaged its dynamic nature while the means of production remained unchanged.

In his analysis the foundation for the Indian feudalism had been obliterated with the collapse of rural community system, which however was restructured in different form what he termed as "semi feudal", particularly after the establishment of the system of "permanent settlement". Thus he wrote:

In the other words, while with the destruction of the village community system the basis of Indian feudalism was reimposed in another form, and therefore, in the British period of her history the agrarian economy of the rural Bengal remained as semi feudal, although it was henceforth made suitable to the demands of commodity production" (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 53)

R.K.M. here interestingly noted that some authors of Marxist paradigm of his contemporary disagreed with the point of re-imposing semi feudal structure on agrarian economy of Bengal which was marked by the emergence of the new production relations. With the concentration of land by few by the means of confiscation as well as expropriation of land from the peasantry and its resultant increase in the number of pauperised cultivators, authors who contradicted on the above point had discovered the fair possibility of establishment of foundation of capitalism in rural Bengal. They were more at ease to classify the rural aggregates into two broad divisions. The ever increasing sharecroppers were considered as 'wage labourers' and the landholders as agrarian capitalists; and "characterise the production relation between a landholder and a sharecropper as that between a capitalist and a proletariat (Mukherjee, 1957, p-53). Here he cited the study of "Problems of Zamindari and Land revenue

Reconstruction in India" by P.N. Driver where he remarked the following passage :

Technically speaking the agricultural labour is one who had no land of any kind to cultivate and who sells his labour power to others in order to earn a living. This automatically excludes any kind of "owner" even a "tenant" from being as the pure proletariat. This technical exclusion, however, hides the real facts about the situation.... If we take a typical Bengali Krishan, for example, there is hardly any doubt that although he is sharer in the final produce he is really a labourer working for a wage which is mainly paid in kind". (Mukherjee, The Dynamics of a Rural Society, 1957, p. p.53)

This so called Marxist explanation for the rise of agrarian capitalism could have been accepted if agrarian capitalism was considered as mere dissociation of peasantry and at the same time "concentration of land" at the hands of few. Capitalism nevertheless suggests a fundamental change from a feudalistic society to a capitalistic one, a change through which agrarian economy could be well organised and structured as well through use of technology in agriculture and "large scale farming and the farm workers are finally reduced to the position of cogs in the wheel of production" (Mukherjee, 1957, pp. p-54) without having any authority and responsibility in the production process.

Disintegration of peasantry, concentration of confiscated lands in the hands of few and increase in commercialization of agricultural products were, of course, the chief factors which had initiated the process of capitalist production in the field of agriculture, these prerequisites discretely or in a set could not alone bring about capitalism, they could only ease the process of initiation of organized agricultural production which would finally lead towards the establishment of the foundation stone of matured capitalism. The above three factors did nothing in Bengal but accentuated the feudalistic exploitation by landholders who burgeoned as parasites outside the rural coherence, and entered into village society with no other intention but to exploit and ransack.

According to R.K.M this semi feudalist era had been persisting even at the threshold of late colonialism in India; moreover concentration of land by the landholders - Zemindars or Jotedars or names whatever they appeared in the scenario of

Bengal, was greater than ever, eventually the landed cultivators became landless sharecroppers, and disintegration of peasantry was accentuated. Such phenomena were seen at best of their strength to bring about an expected structural change between 1941 and 1945 – a period which was marked by the Second world war and famine, he himself was the witness of such devastating epoch when world polity and economy had undergone a process of serious change, rather a sea change. Interestingly, Indian agrarian structure – the relation of production remained same as before. The landholders continued to receive land rent and dissociated peasantry were so inducted to the “Peasant economy” they could not take up any other profession to sell their labour anywhere else, thus they continued with traditional agricultural practices in their small holdings which they were very much attached to. Situation however got slightly changed as landholders arbitrarily posed land rent heavier than ever, “-----and as sharecroppers - the disintegrated peasants were reduced to a position which at least superficially, resembled that of a serf than of a wage - labourer. For, under the existing circumstances, they could not break away from the land and this decadent economy”. (Mukherjee, *The Dynamics of a Rural Society*, 1957)

As a result of such changes a new mode of exploitation by the landholders had been initiated, i.e. landholders allocated a piece of land to the sharecroppers for a term of one year without conferring any tenancy right to them, and with the condition that at the end of term they must provide at least half the share of whatever they would produce, instead of the money value equal to the maximum of ¼th share which was usually taken from cultivators with tenancy right. Thus they were not only deprived of the tenancy right secured by the Tenancy Law which was gained after much struggle (here R.K.M. furnish a short history of struggle for tenancy right : “When the permanent Zemindary Settlement was established in 1793 the Ryots (cultivators) had practically no tenancy right at all, and the landlords were free to impose any rent on them. Bitter struggles between peasants and the overlords over a few decades, which sometimes took the character of rebellion, led up to the passing of the Ryotwari Acts of 1853 and 1858 with many tenancy laws introduced during the period and afterwards”; *The Report of The Land Revenue Commission, volume I and II; and Peasant Uprisings in India: 1850 – 1900, by Natrajan were*

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cited by R.K.M.), but also exploited to its extremity.

He ended up his discussion on the nature and origin of agrarian classes and their relative dependability on economic structure of Bengal, in his book *The Dynamics of A rural Society*, with a conclusion that agrarian society and its corresponding economic structure had never been static, but had always been dynamic. Thus according to him the concept of Bengal’s agrarian class remained the same years after years - is nothing but a myth; on contrary to the colonial scholars and others supporters of the static view, it is dynamic and hence changeable at par with the change in economic structure of agrarian society. Thus one must agree on the point that in order to understand the structure and function of the village society one should not ignore to comprehend thoroughly its economic structure. The rise and demise of social classes at the several points of agrarian history had only indicated the relative change in the economic structure of agrarian society.

Ramakrishna Mukherjee’s concept of agrarian Class structure of Bengal, particularly, its dynamic character at the back drop of self-sufficient village economy during pre British time, and the rise and the demise of some of the agrarian classes under the British rule, and their dependency on economic structure etc, all that he had specified in his major works may be crystallized into few significant points as under for the purpose of critical appreciation:

Classification of agrarian mass into classes: R.K.M’s analysis of agrarian social structure was based on economic interpretation of agrarian stratification of Bengal. His endeavour to apprise agrarian categories through his immaculate presentation of classification scheme was chiefly derived from his concept stemming from Marxian Interpretation of class society,

Class	Sub Class/s	Source of Income	Nature of right
Maliks		From Soil	Ownership
	Big Land Lords	Rent	Property
	Rich Landowners	Rent	property
Kisans			
	Small Land owners	Cultivation	Rights inferior to Malik
	Substantial Tenants	Cultivation	Lease Holder 24
Majdoor			Tenancy right
	Poor Tenants	Cultivation	Less secured right
	Sharecroppers	sharecropping	Lease without security
	Landless Labourers	Wage	No. right on land

through which functioning of the economic structure in agrarian social setup can be measured. Income structure being indicative of economic structure found its expression through per capita income generated mostly from household occupations of the peasant society. He for this reason classified village society under nine(9) occupational categories, the details of which are already appended (see p.3&4) after dividing village mass into nine occupational categories ,he has made a further attempt to delimit his classification into a fewer groups on the point of their related dependency of their respective economic positions. I have presented his classification in a tabular form given below.

	Existence of self Cultivators	Existence share of cropper	Existence of Wage earner
Ramkrishna Mukherjee	Yes	Yes	Yes
Class	Nature of Occupation	Occupational group	
1. Home Landholders	Existence of self-sufficient Occupational group (exp. Artisans, and traders etc.)	1. Landholders	Existence of Poor Tenants
Ramkrishna Mukherjee	Yes	Yes <small>8. Service holders 9. others</small>	No
Daniel Thorner	No	Yes	Yes
	Existence of Sharecroppers	Existence of Landless Labourers	
Ramkrishna Mukherjee	Yes	Yes	
Daniel Thorner	Yes	Yes	

Table I

Classification scheme of Agrarian Mass by Ramkrishna Mukherjee.

Daniel Thorner’ Classification compared:

Daniel Thorner’s classification of agrarian socio-economic categories may be compared with R.K.M’s classification scheme for an in-depth understanding of agrarian socio-economic structure of India and Bengal in specific. While his

classification is based on income generated mostly from the work of household occupational group and their respective position in economic structure, Daniel Thorner’s classification is based on: type of income from the soil; the nature of rights, the extent of the fieldwork carried out in reality.

	Classification scheme based on:	Sub Categories depend on :
Ramkrishna Mukherjee	Income generated from household work from occupational group	occupation
Daniel Thorner	types of Income from soil, nature of rights on soil, extent of fieldwork and their respective position on economic structure	Nature of rights or no right

I have presented Daniel Thorner's classification below in a tabular form:

Table II: Classification scheme of Agrarian Mass by Daniel Thorner

Table III

Compare and Contrast between the Classification Schemes of Ramkrishna Mukherjee and Daniel Thorner

Note:

It is evident from above tables that Daniel Thorner was much more cautious in selecting the foundation for his classification scheme. However, in his watchful attempt no effort is noticeable as to make use of such basis for social category which earns their living from small trade or calling, or of the earning of occupational categories such as cobblers, carpenters, blacksmith ----- etc, who may or may not possess small holdings; however indirectly they associated with agrarian process might be, should they be considered as alien beings to the agrarian economy? Whilst we all

know they had a definite role to play in agrarian production process.

The concept of Malik including two sub concepts :Big Landlords and Rich landowners are somewhat similar to that of R.K.M's Class I category, composed of land holders and supervisory farmers, however the emergence of such class holding property right over land according to R.K.M. was possible only after the establishment of "Permanent Settlement " by The British Emperor. The rich landowners of Bengal were found after "Permanent settlement" 1793; they were mostly outsiders and apathetic to improvement and management of land as they were interested only to accumulate revenues.

3. Ramakrishna Mukherjee's class II scheme is somewhat similar to above classification, however Thorner's classification is based on The nature of rights : (a) Proprietary or ownership,(b) tenancy (with varying degree of tenurial security) etc , and R.K.M's construction of class II is based on self sufficiency , (unlike Thorner) he thus includes Artisans and Traders , "because like the cultivators, most of them barely maintain a somewhat self sufficient existence, partly based on the land" (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 10) .

The classification scheme of Daniel Thorner, specifically Majdur and Kishan (III part of Classification) is almost similar to R.K.M's classification scheme, specifically with The Class III which "is composed of the remaining occupational groups, (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 10)", that means the share croppers, agricultural labourers, service holders and others fall in this category. These occupancy holders are chiefly dependent on the working for other members of society. Few of them exist even on the charity of the better off people in the village.

Thus the point here to remember- while Thorner classified above division mainly on three considerations particularly the "Type of income obtained from the soil", "the nature of rights" and finally "The extent of the fieldwork actually performed" (which are already discussed above), R.K.M categorises The class III on the basis of dependency on the work assigned by other members of society.

Being an eminent Marxist scholar R.K.M identifies class structure of Bengal with their distinctive production relations. He recognizes two sets of production relations were then

predominant in rural Bengal with the advent of British rule. First, the relation between owners of the means of production and the non-owners, viz, sharecroppers, agricultural labourers etc. The means of production in this case is, of course the land, thus he indicates the relation between land owning class, i.e., the class III and the landless class, i.e., the Class I .The relation between users and suppliers of labour. Second," class II as the owner of the means of production and user of own labour. (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 14). Thus he points out that being selfcultivating peasants they not only possessed their own land but also they were dependent on their own labour.thus they stood in some standalone position in the production relation.Daniel Thorner,on the other hand, constructs his three major types on the basis of relation of production, however, he never explicitly specifies but he seems to apply Marxian class model implicitly in his classification scheme. Furthermore while defining subcategories his attention is drawn towards 'the kinds of right and the kinds services' which indicates a Weberian proclivity.

Existence of Village Community and Self sufficient village society

In his endeavour to establish the Class II type in the economy of agrarian Bengal he was evidently dependent on the notion of self sufficient village economy, which according to the most of the scholars, Marxist in particular, prevailed during pre-British India. His perception, as evident from his major works, specifically *The Dynamics of A rural Society* (1957), envisages that the class II type which constituted the soul of Indian village society obviously mirrored the self-sufficient nature of agrarian economy. Tracing the genesis of this type he insisted that the self-sufficient cultivators were predominant in Indian village economy since the distant past, which marked the beginning of the plough-culture. They, however, possessed no property right over the land they tilled, they were authorised only to utilise such land plots which were conferred to them by the village community. According to him the true essence of self-sufficiency was reflected in the authority and function of the Village Community. Throughout the history, from the antiquity of Maurya, Gupta and Post Gupta - through the era of Muslims and Mughals up to the doorstep of colonial imperialism the existence of Village community can be traced to Indian history jointly with the existence of self sufficient cultivators.

Village community remained unchanged over centuries. The question therefore, arises why had village community not been marked by the strain of changes in the equilibrium of power and authority of the nation. He writes:

How did the village community system attain such a stability that it come to be regarded as existing from "time immemorial?" this question should be examined from two aspects, - (i) economic and (ii) social and ideological; viz. one village in relation to other village community and outer world and the other in relation to its internal mechanism. (Mukherjee, 1974, p. 156) .

The first aspect being fundamentally economic in nature , the autarchic village community system was a simplistic organization which was able to retain and uphold the village societies as independent entities and this feature of course enabled them to perpetuate over centuries.

The second was the socio - religious as well as ideological aspect which tended to divide the society under strict stratification manifested in compartmentalization of castes under the hierarchy of Jati division, each of which, according to him, possessed religious sanction in determining their trade and occupation, that is to say the status of groups were determined mainly by their work-related roles. Having thus religious sanction for occupation their hierarchical order remained intact for centuries which unequivocally provided a fundamental basis for the perpetuity of autarchic village community - the autonomous authority which sought to inflict the existence of the occupational hierarchy to maintain their influence and control over the village society for years after year.

The village community was thus a self-governing entity which had authority to decide upon the distribution of land plots and (what) share of crops to be levied as tax given to the government, it played the role of arbitrator in the settlement of land related and other disputes, and it significantly perpetuated through the rise and fall of several dynasties and, it was indifferent even to the dire predicaments like bloodsheds and wars with its great endurance.

The reason for the acceptance of the notion of Self-sufficient village economy and autarchy of Village community by R.K.M is apparently to establish his classification schema

based on the land ownership pattern in combination with household occupation. The landownership pattern in pre-colonial period is claimed (by most of the eminent historians ,economists and other scholars Like Sir Charles Metcalfe, Henry Maine, Karl Marx, Shelvankar, O'Malley ,Gadgil, Buchanan , D.P Mukherji, Altekar etc) to be determined by the autarchic village community. The existence of this village community is hereby concomitant to and logically derived from the notion of self-sufficient village economy. Thus the self sufficient is the major cornerstone for his agrarian class perspective.

Opposed to the concept of self-sufficient Village

Opposed to this notion of self-sufficiency and seclusion of Indian villages M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah wrote :

The idea of the isolation and self sufficiency of Indian Village was first propounded by Sir Charles Metcalfe in 1830, and since then it has had distinguished supporters, scholars as well as politicians. Sir Henry Maines and Karl Marx supported the idea, and in recent time Mahatma Gandhi and his followers not only stated that Indian Village was traditionally self-sufficient but also a political programme which would restore to these villages their pristine self-sufficiency (M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah, 1950, p. 1375).

Thus this is not untrue that Charles Metcalfe's view had been noticeably reflected in the ideas of Henry Maine and Karl Marx. Both of the stalwart scholars made it a code of belief, rather a doctrinaire base for interpretation as well as analysis of Indian agrarian society at pre - British period.

The true nature of Indian rural society, village community in particular, according to them , seemed to unravel its characteristics which demonstrated its dependency on several issues rather than its self-sufficiency and self reliance nature :

M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah exemplified the exhaustive works on the village communities by the skilled anthropologists as well as sociologists who since last twenty years , had fortunately come across historical data which disclosed that roads, particularly inter village roads, were poorly developed because of inadequacy of monetization of village economy as a whole. It gave a clear picture that, "the village was always part of a

wider economic, political and religious system. The appearance of isolation, autonomy and self sufficiency was only an illusion". (M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah, 1950, p. 1375). It was also evident that in some parts of the country like coastal Kerala, Coorg, highland Gujarat and in some other places villages were not found nucleated and dispersed.

The 'village' in the above areas constructed with a number of discrete farms and possessor of a farm or his representative living on his farm. The dispersed village was not; therefore, a clear entity like the nucleated village. There was no perceptible boundary between one village and another. "The members living in it are served by artisan and servicing castes from several dispersed villages. That is each artisan caste serves a distinct group of villages; and the village may be represented by a series of partially overlapping circles". (M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah, 1950, p. 1376)

According to them "The administrative and 'social' villages are not always identical even in areas with nucleated settlements. An administrative village occasionally includes more than one social village while a social village is more rarely divided into more than one administrative village (M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah, 1950, p. 1376).

This is very true that villages had no clearcut boundaries, and they often overlapped each other. Not only artisans but also other occupational castes catered their services to other villages or a group of villages; and importance of the distinction between administrative village/s and social villages can not be ignored. With such examples cited by Srinivas and Shah the claim of isolated and nucleated village needs evidential reassurance.

Srinivas and Shah envisaged through their article (1950) that the kinship and marital ties across villages also laid the foundation of cohesive bondages. In this respect, it is obviously important to remember that intra village marriages were more or less unconventional even in south Indian villages where cross-cousin and cross-uncle-niece marriages were pre-dominant. Convention of such marriages was seen only at inter-village level and hardly at intra-village level; and in Bengal also inter-village marriage was preferred than intra-village marriage.

Thus from the above view their point seems to appear that a huge number of villages were communally associated as well as ethnically dependent on each other through kinship and marital ties and hence the villages were not entirely unconnected to each other.

Weekly market or hat in pre-British time was another point which disclosed the mutual existence of villages and their dependency on each other through sales transactions as well as exchange of things among them. The weekly market was a kind of phenomenon which had quite proudly manifested their entities since the antiquity, even till date. Thus with a collective spirit villagers belonged to many a villages congregated for the purpose of the sales and purchase, thus a mutual dependence was not very rare within a host of villages in the same locale. Village craftsmen more often than not went to other places: villages or towns, to vend products.

Srinivas and Shah observed that the pilgrims were found to be moving places beyond boundaries of their own villages and the places of pilgrimage such as temples, mosques or religious places which were (still are) surrounded by shops, and fairs of various type, associated with seasonal festivity. Few fairs were as attractive as religious one such as cattle fair where people used to come covering a large distance for a gainful exchange.

The pattern of land ownership was another point they discovered which recognised no limit of village boundary. The owner of a piece of land might not always belong to the same village, he might belong to neighbouring village also; the record of absentee land owners, who possessed lands in villages but resided in urban areas, was not very rare since last few hundred years, agrarian labours frequently went to other nearby villages for the search of jobs; Srinivas and Shah, thus quite opposed to the idea forwarded by Charles Metcalf subsequently accepted by Henry Maine and Marx that village societies were "Little republics" isolated and self-sufficient.

External trade is another important point where the notion of self sufficiency contradicts to a great extent. Srinivas and Shah disagreed with the notion which was almost taken for granted to a host of scholars who believed Indian villages were complete virgin of trade and commerce.

Inter-regional trade is a point similarly contrasted to the idea of self-sufficiency of villages. According to them inter regional exchange of agrarian and forest produces took place among villages and also between villages and towns.

Dependence on towns is one more point they attached in their article to comprehend whether agrarian society was dependent on urban society, if at all how and to what degree? According to them, while urban society was dependent on agrarian society for agrarian produces such as food grains, handicrafts etc, agrarian people were also dependent on urban market for some sophisticated city products as well as some specialised services which a city or some large city-like settlement could only provide.

Political structure is a further point through which they established the fact that villages and towns were intricately linked by an extensive power grid. It was however commonly assumed that villages were not predisposed to the function of polity. Opposed to this idea they offered the concept of Dominant Caste. The Dominant Caste as conceived by Srinivas was such a caste which wielded political power by the means of ownership as well as concentration of huge cultivable lands. The dominant caste was placed below the higher echelons in the authoritarian hierarchy of polity. Srinivas further added that leading caste members being placed at the lower level hierarchy was responsible to uphold and recognise the pre-eminence of power of the upper level.

Two more points raised by these scholars against self sufficiency are worthy to mention here. First refers to the Conflict between Rajputs and Muslims in Gujrat. Rajputs were a dominant caste before 13th Century, when Gujrat was reigned by Rajputs and they were numerically high in the entire region.

When the Muslim conquerors removed the sovereign king of Gujarat all the lower chieftains fought the Muslims. The Persian chronicles, Mirat - i - Sikandari,¹¹ Mirat'i-Ahmadi¹² and Ferista¹ bear eloquent testimony to the relentless fight put up by the local Rajput chieftains (called Girasiyas) and their allies, the Koli chieftains, for over 400 years. (M.N. Srinivas and A.M. Shah, 1950)

Thus this historical fact refers quite clearly to the point that intra-racial consolidation

helped Rajputs and their allies to continue a four hundred years long battle against Muslims. Second is the point which evidently asserts several facts in favour of inter-dependence of villages. Apart from various occasions like pilgrimages and festivities, religions, Hinduism in particular among other major religious faith, hugged their members so tight that a country wide religious solidarity was achieved. This solidarity knew no boundary. A pan-Hinduism or Sanscritic Hinduism found its embodiment through the interpretation and explanation of the Ramayana, Mahabharata and Bhagavata Gita to the village dwellers by the Brahman priests who circuitously helped the process of Sanskritisation

All of the above points they joted down unravelled the fact that Indian villages had always been parts of a wider system. The worst road conditions, heavy monsoon, incongruous economic exchange marked by barter system, cohesive entity of village communities and villagers strong sense of belonging etc, all these produced illusories and deceptive views of self-sufficiency and of isolation of villages.

Eventually, they established their view that the notion of self sufficiency of the Indian villages – the very idea conceived and augmented by Charles Metcalfe which later gained unequivocal ground in the theories of Henry Maine and Karl Marx – was nothing but the saga which took a position deep seated in the psyche of scholars. Thus the uncultivated as well as non-verified hypothesis became popular and was taken for granted by the researchers and academicians as a comprehensive tool for their own interpretation of village society

Thus from the above angle R.K.M. may be criticised for choosing such an incoherent base in his attempt to interpret Indian village society, Bengal in particular and thereby to comprehend the class division and relation in the agrarian social settings. Though implied, R.K.M's emphasis was apparently placed more on the peasants (class II) who exploited none but their own labour to cultivate for their bare subsistence, thus they attained a self sufficient character; and Self sufficient farmers were predominant in India since pre British time. A collectivity of such self-sufficient peasants and also rural artisans (more or less self reliant) constituted the majority of village economy structure, the trail of which could be traced even to British era in the year 1946(see Pie Charts I, II & III).

It is evident that his understanding of village economic structure is dependant more on the notion of "self-sufficient" and "autarchic village community". His intention was quite clear that he wanted to prove the continuity of existence of self cultivating peasants whose property right were not established, but land utilization right was ascribed by the village community whose claim of authority was not de jure but de facto. Land utilization right was thus inherited by the self sufficient peasants generation wise. Though rare, the land might be alienated or handed over to someone else.

In search of the fact why right to land property was not established among cultivating peasants he traced back to history where he found that, since post samhita period to Buddhist period, the higher caste Hindus impelled certain conditions under which lower castes had to serve by toiling on lands of upper castes, and such settings were unaffected even in the Buddhist period when lower stratum served the Monks by voluntary agricultural practices in the lands of Samgha within or outside the precinct of Monastery.

Sudras, Dasas or conquered enemies as well as aboriginals, who formed the lower strata, were predestined to toil on the lands of the upper stratum. Because the agriculture was not a legitimate practice for upper stratum neither they were appreciated by the society. Land labourers of such kind who toiled "others' land without themselves having any usufructuary or property right over the holding were apparently present throughout the pre-British period of India's history" (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 16). The above fact was evident from the studies of the officers of The East India Company. Here he made two references significant to his point : H.T. Colebrooke's Remarks on the Husbandary and Internal Commerce of Bengal ,p.91 ; and Francis Buchanan-Hamilton's A Survey of the Zila in Dinajpoors etc.

However, the above practice of toiling on land of other higher stratum by the lower stratum should not be equated with the practice of sharecropping or hiring land labours which was essentially temporal only to British period onwards. According to him characteristics of sharecropping and land labour hiring were completely absent in pre British era and self cultivating peasants utilizing a piece of land on a hereditary basis were the only producing category predominant in ancient India. This institutional

setup persisted through Muslim period to the commencement of British Raj.

Questions may here be raised that, if, according to him, lower strata of the rural society served the upper caste by tilling soil without any established authority on lands and if such arrangement continued till the initiation of British rule, should we then consider that the self cultivating farmers emerged from such an arrangement perpetuated through the ages?

However, he along with above fact identified some other source of emergence of class-II; he in line with Marxist view insisted that the lands, arable or arid, in pre-British period were communally owned. The village community was a hamlet with greater autonomy to decide the distribution of lands (to class II). The existence autarchic of village is of course a debatable issue but one has also to agree that without this the existence self cultivating peasants were unconceivable, in the sense who would then authorise them with usufructuary right to lands while kings or peshewas were never involved with the distribution or redistribution of lands ? Their interests were limited to only land revenues.

Mode of Landownership : As discussed at the various points of his discourse that lands were acquired from village community by the self-cultivating peasants for the purpose of their subsistence production. The ownership of these lands were not however, proprietary but usufructuary ,i.e., the farmers had lands utilization right only. These lands could be inherited , alienated and, though infrequent but not exceptional , transferred to others. Village communities, during pre-British period, were a kind of de facto authority who would distribute or redistribute lands to the class II farmers. Thus he assured that no land property was till then established and lands were communally held by the village authority. It had enormous control over the activities of village.

the "jurisdiction of the village authorities extended over the houses, streets, bazars, barning grounds, temples, wells, tanks, waste lands, forests and cultivable lands"; that the village council " looked after village defence, settled village disputes, organised work of public utility, acted as a trustee of the minors and collected the government revenues and paid them into the central treasury" ; and that the central state governments " could eventually reach the people

and discharge their functions mainly through these bodies" (Mukherjee, 1957, p. 18)

The right of land ownership was absolutely usufructuary to prove this point R.K.M. analysed historical data with following evidences:

First, within sixth to seventeenth century, the ownership of the land carried great social honour to individuals, thus individuals irrespective of their trades or callings aspired to have at least a small holding; but at the same time a system of periodical redistribution of arable lands was prevalent in the several places of the country. This was eventually an indicative of fact that the term ownership of land was most likely to mean a kind of land utilization right or usufructuary right which a fortunate individual might entitle.

Second, historically the land alienation was not an uncommon phenomenon in India. Lands were mainly endowed to the spiritual heads such as Brahmins or religious institutes as ceremonial gifts. However, in this case, they did not get hold of the lands, they were only entitled to receive Royal revenues in order to sustain their religious activities. It is evident from fact above that the transfer of ownership was in reality the transfer of revenues; no property right was admissible to recipients.

Third, apart from the religious gift the land right was also transferred in case of land remaining vacant or untenanted for the want of successors or incapability of paying land taxes.

Fourth, in spite of some stray cases of land alienation and transfer as stated above, the socio-economic conditions of Indian village during 200 to 550 AD were such that it disapproved absentee landlordism.

He therefore drew conclusion from the above facts that lands were owned in ancient India not terms of property right but in terms of right to land utilization for the purpose of their own sustenance.

The concept of feudalism is very much associated with the nature of landownership right. To understand the nature of Indian feudalism Prof. D.D. Kosambi traced the nature of landownership pattern dates back to the Mauryan period. The main theme of the Mauryan dynasty was:

all lands belongs to the king which was underpinned by the "tribal concept of land as

territory (not property) held in common by the tribe, whose symbol and expression was the chief; this chief would be replaced by the king ,(Arth, 11.1) or turn into a king , or be converted into a feudal tributary by conqueror who might at need support the chieftain against its former tribesmen. (Kosambi, 1978)

It is important to consider D.D. Kosambi's view of land ownership in pre-British time. He insisted that Indian feudalism varies in many ways from its European complements, particularly on the question "who owns the land". Which had no clear cut answer.

According to Kosambi a new type of ownership was thus gradually established on land which was equivalent to (bourgeois) property right which was manifested in various customary forms and was guaranteed and legitimised by payment of land taxes.

From the above view of Kosambi it may be said that ownership right of lands were assured by the law, upheld by a systematic judiciary arrangement and reinforced by system of law enforcement. It was therefore, no less a private property right on land as in bourgeois terms.

M.N. Srinivas while establishing his notion of "Dominant Caste" claimed that land ownership right was essential to caste dominance. To Srinivas ,"For a caste to be dominant, it should own a sizable amount of arable land locally available, have strength of numbers and occupy a high place in the local hierarchy" (Srinivas, 1972). Out of three major components Landownership (two others were; the caste should have numerical strength and should occupy a higher place in caste hierarchy in the locality) was vitally important to him, because, "Landownership confers not only power but prestige, so much so that individuals who have made good in any walk of life tend to invest in land. If landownership is not always indispensable passport to high rank, it certainly facilitates upward mobility" (Srinivas, 1972).

M.N. Srinivas thus acknowledged the importance of landownership for the notion of dominant caste; he however, never clarified the nature or the pattern of landownership i.e., proprietary or usufructuary right to land, a dominant caste possessed or should possess. Pointing to land concentration by Dominant Caste he wrote that: ---- the pattern of landownership in rural India is such that the bulk of the arable land

is concentrated in the hands of a relatively small number of big owners against a large number who either own very little land or no land at all (Srinivas, 1972).

Through the above statement it is understood that he indicated towards the private ownership of lands as well as the concentration of land by the dominant castes. Thus he hinted towards the idea of persistence of institution of property right in agrarian social settings.

According to Upendra Nath Ghosal in ancient India Rig Veda (Samhita) illustrated that cultivable lands in Indo-Aryan society were held under individual possession or family ownership, whereas community ownership was limited merely to meadows or grass land. Private ownership of land was undoubtedly a recognised institution. Secondly, Land possessed by the individuals who cleared the forest and brought the land under cultivation, could sell, donate, present, or leave at their own disposal. Thirdly, "There was a clear distinction between ownership rights and restricted real estate rights " (Ghoshal, 1973).

It appears from the above that in India the principle of private property and private ownership of land has been recognised from ancient times. At the same time, there was nothing called absolute ownership of land. Individuals or groups of individuals enjoyed ownership with respect to land, but the ruler had the supreme power to levy taxes as a price of protection and not ownership. (Ghoshal, 1973) (Chakraborty, 2006)

The proprietary right on arable lands was a contradictory issue on which the scholars could never be unequivocal, while the idea received well acceptance by some scholars, most of them refuted the possibility of such private arrangements of lands with a forceful denial.

In Muslim period, however, the assessment of land tax system was most suitably organised and methods of measurement of arable lands were systematised and arrangement and categorization of land depending on survey of productivity were first introduced.

Muslim period was, therefore, marked by the systematization of land revenue method and structure; however all through its time span it never endeavoured to establish or reconstruct the pattern of ownership on lands, it simply encouraged reinforcement on perpetuating

system of landownership by the revenue structure which guaranteed the protection of lands.

The word "Malik" (owner) took its origin from the Farsi word *Milkiyat* which means ownership. Thus the ownership "in agricultural land under the Mughals was not, according to Habib, the same as 'ownership' as understood today. The raiyat had no right to alienate his land freely. Cultivation as a right was vested hereditarily in the peasant, but it was also an obligation from which no peasant was exempt" (Raychaudhuri Tapan, 1986).

It is apparent from Habib's view that property right on land was not established even at the Mughal period. Ownership of land as well as "ryotwari" in this period was rather obligatory, for the ryots who were not authorised to alienate land by the means of selling, nor even could they simply alienate the land.

Habib opposing the view of community ownership or the distribution of arable lands wrote

There is not 'the slightest suggestion anywhere in our sources' that the occupancy or proprietary right was ever held in common or land distributed periodically; the village community developed only in 'some spheres outside that of production.' (Habib, 1963)

Habib's assertion is, however, contrasted with the views of Charles Metcalfe and many other British officials in the beginning of the 19th century who through their reports emphasised on the fact of communal ownership and periodic redistribution of lands by the village council.

In this connection it is important to add that the genesis of Indian village community which could be traced to the archaic tribal social organization. Scholars insisted on the fact that arable lands were shaped by removing forests largely through tribal's initiative. Eventually, the ownership of the lands belonged to the tribes which were the earlier forms of village community systems and thus a common ownership of the land was established. Tracing the origin of ownership of the land D. Chattopadhyay in his article "Village Community" wrote that, though Engel differentiated between tribal and village community however he assured the existence of these pre-class entities in India

which in turn emerged as village communities, and persisted till the British took-over.

The early British Reports on the Revenue and Settlement were the chief sources of the writings of Wilks, Campbell and Maine emphasised on the fact that: this characteristic of the primitive pre-class society, namely the common ownership of the land, continued to persist as a living feature of the village communities, even when these communities were much ahead of the strictly tribal stage. (Chattopadhyay, 1969, p. 158).

The validity of chief feature of the village community, i.e., common ownership was challenged time and again; standing in forefront Baden-Powell controverted the notion of collective ownership by referring to Ryotwari village; however he admitted the existence of some Joint Village which resembled the Henry Maine's idea of common ownership. D. Chattopadhyay most amusingly noted:

Strangely enough, Baden-Powell, though so anxious to disprove collective-ownership of the land, did not argue against the survival of the tribal elements in these villages of ryotwari type. On the contrary, one of the specific points of his criticism of Maine was the latter overlooked the tribal survival of these villages. (Chattopadhyay, 1969, p. 159)

Thus from the above assertion it is well understood that Baden-Powell unintentionally though, accepted the tribal element in the ryotwari villages which points to the hint of common ownership of land, because the tribal element was itself the indicator of common possession of land.

Conclusion

Ramakrishna Mukherjee's perspective on the dynamism of rural economic structure till British colonial period characterised by class structure was examined comparatively and critically. His interpretation of agrarian class society was no doubt originated from Marxist class view. In his analysis of agrarian socio-economic structure he, though not uniquely, placed occupation holders in the mainstream agrarian economy, which some scholars intentionally or unintentionally ignored, for occupation holders like village artisans, according to them had a little to contribute in agrarian economy directly.

His complete dependency on self sufficiency of village community raised some legitimate questions which further gained strong ground with Srinivas and Shah's sharp criticisms. But both the scholars never denied the presence of "Self-cultivating" peasants which quite reflected the very attribute of the village community (they apparently ignored). More over the village societies in pre British era were not all the same everywhere. Pre-British Indian agrarian societies were vastly differentiated by their nature, thus a mere generalisation of either self-sufficient cum isolated or dependent cum cohesive village societies would have always been subjective and value loaded. However, the presence of self sufficient peasantry in pre British agrarian society or ryots was undeniable; and subsistence production of self cultivating peasants reflected the very nature, i.e., self sufficiency of the peasant community; absolute isolation of the villages was thus a secondary question. Historically it is not untrue that self sufficient village economy was shattered by Permanent Settlement of 1793, and eventually ryots were gradually demised with the introduction of "Property right on land", and with the advent of new propertied class, share cropper, land labour class the old class structure transformed to new one, which offered a dynamism to a centuries old static agrarian economic structure.

Changes in the pattern of ownership of land was perhaps most vital to the causes of dynamism in rural economic structure. After Permanent Settlement (1793) a tendency towards Legal appropriation of lands was increased among a section of affluent class in Bengal, and eventually lands were concentrated in hands of few, which led to emerge a proprietary class (who were mostly absentee landlords), along with other agrarian classes, viz sharecroppers and landless labourers displacing the old system and posed a semi feudal arrangement in agrarian economy. In this way, he explained the dynamism of agrarian class structure together with its economic structure of almost every part of rural India and Bengal in particular.

Although it is hard to assess Ramakrishna Mukherjee's contribution towards understanding of structural dynamics of agrarian society of colonial Bengal, an appraisal on the above may be offered as under.

I think that Ramakrishna Mukherjee's interpretation towards structural dynamics of agrarian society of Bengal was factual to a certain extent barring few dogmas which are already discussed above at several points. His attempt at stratification of agrarian society was considerably and comparatively conspicuous. Being a doctrinaire communist his interpretation of class division of agrarian India had some obvious lean on the perception of Karl Marx, influenced chiefly (as he told the author in an Interview taken during a session - June 2015*) from Marx's article, "on India"; and also from Correspondence (1934) by Marx & Engels. His agrarian class division was based primarily on Charles Metcalfe's notion of "Self-sufficient village community" in pre-British days supported by Marx and Maine. To establish such a view he pointed to the fact that very many authors took efforts to bear out that Indian agrarian economic structure was unaffected by the changes in dynasty; even after the advent of British rule it remained the same. They pointed to the individuals who, without any kind of land ownership toiled in the process of agricultural production against the payment in cash or kind, had been persisted since antiquity. The entity of such land labours throughout the Indian agrarian history, even in the British period the evidence of which was supported by the early British officials in their reports, scholars from the fields of History and Sociology tended to equate those labours of ancient time with the wage labours of British period. This was done by those scholars who were myopic to the fact that the indispensable character of wage labourers was to produce commodities; they were the products of commodification of agriculture. This was absent in pre British time. According to R.K.M. the self sufficient peasants were "practically the only producing type" predominant in agrarian India, Bengal in particular till the commencement of land settlement by British. The self-sufficient peasants were the products of self-sufficient village communities because village communities assigned them lands to cultivate and further these lands were occupied hereditarily by them and the ownerships were legitimised by revenue payment on regular basis. His class II thus formed with self sufficient peasants and occupation-holders. Thus it was apparent that together with ryots and village artisans, self sufficient village economies had been lasted for centuries and never disrupted until the advent of British rule.

These are the realities Ramakrishna Mukherjee understood with his strong insights and

painstaking village studies like "Six Villages ". He stayed in villages for long and walked miles after miles to examine the nature of village community and their existential lives, endured all the pains and sufferings as village folks suffered, accepted all usual miseries of village life only to comprehend their socio-economic position in reality.

Pie Charts below are prepared from the data available from collected in 1946 by the Indian Statistical Institute which were cited Dr. Ramkrishna Mukherjee in The Dynamics of a Rural Society, 1957 p-9 & 12 .

Pie Chart I

Pie Chart II

Pie chart III

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Keywords and Glossary

Absentee Landlordism: An institutionalised practice of a few landholders who were never present in their lands to supervise agriculture.

Affluent Non-Cultivating: the term represents a section of the rich people who possessed the arable lands but they never cultivated their own lands.

**Agrarian Relations of Production
Agricultural Labourers**

Alienation

Alienated Peasants: The farmers who were estranged from their lands for the burden of tax during British period.

Artisans:

Autarchic Village Community:.

British Industrial Trade Policy

British Merchant Capital

City Workers

Class Structure:

Commercial Crops:

Commercialisation of Agriculture:

Commodification:

Commodity Production:

Community Wealth:

Company or East India Company : Here it refers to the mercantile organization of the Great Britain, *the East India Company*. The company started to develop trade in East Indies (the islands off the south-eastern coast of Asia, including Java and Borneo). By the 18th century it had its own army and political service, and was responsible for the administration of the parts of India. (Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary, 2013)

Culture-Lag

Disintegration of Peasantry

Egalitarian: The notion that everyone is equal and should have the same rights and opportunities. The word is used in this article conjointly with society, which means a society without much stratification.

Equitable Distribution:

Estate Farming: In a commercial based agriculture, crops are raised in large scale

plantations or estates and shipped off to other countries for money.

Fifth Report of British Parliament: it consists of Select Committee Reports from 1805 to 1874 documenting the operations of the East India Company and its administration of the colony and constituting some of the most valuable primary sources for the study of nineteenth-century India. Key years in the company's history were 1813 and 1833 when its Charter was renewed by parliament and 1858 when the Charter was withdrawn. (Source: http://www.britishparliamentarypapers.com/acatalog/East_India.html)

Indian Feudalism: Few scholars tried to employ the word *Indian Feudalism* to indicate the Indian agrarian system within the time frame of pre British as well as British era (Mughal era in particular). Through this they seemed to have imported the idea of European feudalism in the medieval period, in accordance with such an imported idea, the landed nobility possessed the lands from the Crown in lieu of military services when it was asked for and vassals were, in turn, tenants of the nobles, while the peasants or serfs were obliged to live on their lord's land and to give him homage, labour, and a share of produces, notionally in exchange for military protection. Thus, the term *Indian feudalism* is an attempt to classify Indian history according to a European model.

Industrial Capital: British Mercantile investment in India for the development of industry.

Jati is a Hindu caste or a distinctive social group of which there are thousands throughout India; a special characteristic is often the exclusive occupation of its male members (such as barber or potter). Professor Madhav Gadgil (1983) has described Jatis as self-governing, closed communities, based on his research in rural Maharashtra.

Jotedars/Jotdars: The Jotedars or Jotdars were the section of landed gentry of the rural Bengal. They were also known as *haoladars* or *gantidars* in other provinces. They were the revenue collectors, however, the Jotedars not only used to collect revenues but also involved in money lending trade. A large section of Bengal peasantry used to borrow money from the Jotedars to meet the high land revenues.

Land Alienation: Estrangement of land by the owner or cultivator.

Landed Gentry: Owners class of land properties

Little Republics: Charles Metcalfe in his account (1830) village communities had been described as little republics or small democratic states almost independent of any external control.

Majdoors: Those who earn their livelihood primarily, from working on others lands/plots.

Mauryan Dynasty: The Maurya Empire was a geographically most widespread imperial domain in ancient India, ruled by the Maurya dynasty from 322–185 BCE.

Means of Production:

Means of Subsistence: The minimal resources that are necessary for survival.

Pauperization : it denotes the process of impoverishment of working class by the exploitation of capitalists ; it is here utilized as the process of impoverishment of the self cultivating farmers or the ryot class, and their transformation to landless labours.

Permanent Settlement : The Permanent Settlement as well as the Permanent Settlement of Bengal in Bengali *Chirosthayi Bandobasto* which was an agreement between the East India Company and Bengali landlords in the year 1793 to fix revenues to be collected from the peasantry of Bengal. Through this act landlords as well as zemindars were employed permanently to collect tax from their territory which eventually established their proprietary right on land.

Private Property

Production Relations

R.K.M.: Abbreviated name of Ramkrishan Mukherjee

Report of The Indian Statutory Commission:

The Indian Statutory Commission was a group of seven British Members of Parliament of United Kingdom that had been sent to India in 1928 to study constitutional reform in Britain's most important colonial dependency. It was commonly referred to as the Simon Commission after its chairman, Sir John Simon.

Ryot: Ryot alternatively known as raiyat, or ravat was a general economic term used throughout India for peasant cultivators but with variations in different provinces. While zamindars were landlords, raiyats were tenants and cultivators.

Ryotwari : The ryotwari system, instituted in some parts of India, was one of the main systems used to collect revenues from the cultivators of agricultural land. These revenues included undifferentiated land taxes and rents, collected simultaneously.

Samgha is a word derived from Pali and Sanskrit to mean "association", "assembly", "company" or "community" and associated mostly with Buddhism to refer the monastic community of ordained Buddhist monks or nuns.

Sanccritisation is a particular form of social change found in India. It denotes the process by which castes placed lower in the caste hierarchy seek upward mobility by emulating

the rituals and practices of the upper or dominant castes. It is a process similar to passing in sociological terms

Sharecroppers

Subha of Bengal means a province (here Bengal) of the Mughal Empire between the 16th and 18th centuries.

Subinfeudatory : In English law, subinfeudation is the practice by which tenants, holding land under the king or other superior lord, carved out new and distinct tenures in their turn by sub-letting or alienating a part of their lands.

Sudras : A member of the lowest of the four major castes of traditional Indian society, comprising artisans, labourers, and menials.

Surplus

The Dominant Caste

Usufructuary: The usufructuary never had possession of the property (on the basis that if he possessed at all, he did so through the owner), but he did have an interest in the property itself for a period, either a term of years, or a lifetime. (source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Usufruct>). Here the ryot or self cultivating class in the pre British period had hereditary ownership on the piece of land, which was further legitimised by the payment of land revenue to representative of the Crown. They however, had only land utilization right, not the right to land property.

Zemindars